

APPROACH TO SOLVING EXPERIMENTAL PROBLEMS BASED ON SYSTEM ANALYSIS

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada eksperimental masalalarga tizimli tahlil asosida yondashuv imkoniyatlari tahliliy bayon etilgan. Unda eksperimental masalalarga muammoli vaziyatning modeli sifatida yondashuvga oid o'ziga xos jihatlarini yoritishga urg'u berilib, ularga e'tibor qaratish didaktik maqsadga erishishda ahamiyatli ekanligi asoslangan.

Kalit so'zlar: eksperimental masala, tizimli tahlil, fikrlash texnikasi, didaktik maqsad, modellar, ramziy til.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлены возможности системно-аналитического подхода к экспериментальным задачам. Основное внимание в ней уделяется выделению специфических аспектов подхода к экспериментальным вопросам как модель проблемной ситуации, и обосновано, что внимание к ним важно для достижения дидактической цели.

Ключевые слова: экспериментальная проблема, системный анализ, техники мышления, дидактическая цель, модели, символический язык.

Abstract: This article presents the possibilities of the system-analytical approach to experimental tasks. The main attention is paid to the identification of specific aspects of the approach to experimental issues as a model of a problem situation, and it is substantiated that attention to them is important for achieving the didactic goal.

Keywords: experimental problem, system analysis, thinking techniques, didactic goal, models, symbolic language.

When chemical information is acquired by learners and re-explained, it turns into knowledge, if they can solve similar problems, it turns into skills, if they solve modified problems, it turns into skills. experimental issues play an important role in raising the level of competence. An experiential problem is a model of a problematic situation, which differs from calculation-based problems in that, in addition to thinking knowledge, knowledge and skills related to practical activities based on chemical laws are also required. In order to solve experimental problems, in addition to mastering theoretical knowledge, students should also have sufficient information about experimental processes,

conditions, signs, devices, and reagents. In this process, students continue to expand and deepen their knowledge of chemistry, while also forming special skills for conducting experiments. One of the most important aspects of solving experimental problems is that it helps students to develop their independent work skills and forms such characteristics as being orderly, attentive, careful, observant, self-confidence, and striving for a goal.

Experiential problems are the best tool for expanding students' thinking, they make sure that behind abstract formulas there are substances with certain properties, they can be familiarized with these properties, study them, and use them in practice. Before performing the experiment, the students determine the way to perform the work for themselves, think about the necessary reagents, equipment, and devices. While observing the process, he pays special attention to the properties of substances, their changes, signs of reactions, the final result, summarizes his thoughts and draws a conclusion. Solving experimental problems is also an important tool for monitoring students' acquired knowledge and skills [1, 2]. Experimental problems can be widely used not only during practical training, but also at all stages of chemistry education, in the processes of explanation, reinforcement, generalization, repetition, control. The possibilities of using experimental problems within the framework of chemical science, chemical circles, additional training, independent work, home experiments are very high. [3].

Experimental problems can be organized by the teacher or student in the form of a demonstration experiment, in the form of joint work of students of all classes, in the form of experimental control tasks or homework.

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Table 1.
Systematic analysis of experimental issues.

<p>1. Placing the exercise Determining the essence of the problem. Determining the goal and solution boundaries of the problem</p>	<p>Make the following changes and isolate the copper (II) hydroxide from the resulting mixture. $CuO \rightarrow CuSO_4 \rightarrow Cu(OH)_2$</p> <p>The question of the type of acquisition of substances of experimental problems. Properties of oxides. Extraction of salts. Properties and extraction of bases.</p>
<p>2. Summarizing data (gathering information and identifying alternatives to achieve the goal)</p>	<p>Reaction of copper (II) oxide with acids. Reaction of copper (II) sulfate with alkalis. Copper (II) hydroxide is a water-insoluble precipitate.</p>
<p>3. Explanation (comments according to the structure of the model and its application)</p>	<p>$CuO + H_2SO_4 \rightarrow CuSO_4 + NaOH \rightarrow Cu(OH)_2$</p>
<p>3. Recommendation (recommending a preferred alternative solution option or process)</p>	<p>1) $CuO + H_2SO_4 = CuSO_4 + H_2O$ 2) $CuSO_4 + NaOH = Cu(OH)_2 \downarrow + Na_2SO_4$</p>
<p>5. Confirmation (checking the solution, conducting an experiment)</p>	<p>When sulfuric acid solution is added to copper (II) oxide powders, a blue solution ($CuSO_4$) is formed. When sodium hydroxide solution is added dropwise to the formed solution, air forms a colored precipitate ($Cu(OH)_2$). The precipitate is separated from the solution by filtration.</p>

Teaching students to analyze the conditions of the problem, to determine the type of its structure and the method of its solution is the most important condition for the formation of generalized skills in solving computational problems [4]. Experiential training made it possible to eliminate the usual difficulties in solving various problems, including problems of "acquired

difficulties", and to form the ability to solve different types of problems with a significant reduction in the number of problems of the same type solved in training. When using the proposed model, it becomes possible to include issues of the school course that are not provided for in traditional education. The formation of the ability to analyze the conditions of the problem with the help of the proposed method opens the possibility to the student to systematically select all objects, their parameters and connections, which ultimately allows to build a chain of calculations to narrow down the desired result. As a result of the given recommendation, students organize systematic analysis and problem-solving activities, and theoretical thinking with a systematic direction is formed. The obtained results show the prospects of this approach and allow us to hope for the success of its application in solving wider problems in various disciplines. It becomes clear that there is a need for research on the change of motivation in solving problems, the principles of building systems of educational tasks, the characteristics of using educational tools in organizing activities, and the way is opened. The use of systematic analysis in the organization of solving experimental problems helps to develop theoretical, practical, creative knowledge and skills.

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